

Astronomy Education Teacher Training Standards

Pilot Study Report
April 2022

A photograph of the Aurora Borealis (Northern Lights) in a snowy mountain landscape. The aurora is a vibrant green, flowing across the dark blue night sky. Below, snow-covered mountains and a rocky shoreline are visible under a clear blue sky.

“

I touch the future. I teach.

Christa McAuliffe

“

Es ist die wichtigste Kunst des Lehrers, die Freude am Schaffen und am Erkennen zu wecken“

“It is the most important art of the teacher to awaken the joy of creating and recognising.”

Albert Einstein

Images credit: ESO/HdA

CONTENTS

Summary	4
Introduction	5
Aim of the study	6
Methodology	6
Results	7
Demographics	7
<i>Survey respondents</i>	7
<i>Teacher training instructors</i>	8
<i>Teachers attending training</i>	8
Training workshops	10
<i>Instruction methods in teacher training</i>	11
<i>Resources used in teacher training</i>	11
<i>Observational activities in teacher training</i>	13
Post workshops	15
Discussion	16
Content standards	17
Teaching method standards	18
Resource standards	19
Accreditation standards	19
Educator standards	20
Concerns and challenges	21
Conclusion	22
References	23

Images credit: ESA/ESERO Netherlands

Summary

This report presents the initial findings from an exploratory study, with the aim of highlighting key characteristics that can be used to inform the development of consensus standards for educators organising Astronomy Education workshops. These standards will provide the groundwork for an iterative in-depth study. The ultimate aim being the synthesis of a framework for high-quality astronomy education teacher training standards, through consensus from both the astronomy and education communities.

This study used an online questionnaire to seek insights from members of the International Astronomical Union (IAU), and its extended network which includes the offices: Office of Astronomy for Development (OAD), Office of Astronomy for Outreach (OAO), and Office of Astronomy for Education (OAE), and their relevant networks.

The analysis, although being grounded in a mixed-methods approach, was driven primarily by a qualitative lens. The aim was to identify overarching patterns or themes that could potentially form the foundations for a framework of Astronomy Education Teacher Training Standards (AETTS). Using this approach, five overarching themes were identified: Content Standards, Teaching Method Standards, Resource Standards, Accreditation Standards, and Educator Standards; together with the concerns and challenges associated with developing standards.

Introduction

The process of teaching and learning is complex, layered and affected by various internal and external factors that involves the interaction of teachers, students, and the broader community (Shuell, 2001) . Teaching is more than merely inducting students in the content knowledge of the subject, rather it is about supporting students to develop their epistemic practices, and diverse ways of knowing. But most importantly teaching needs to be contextual and relevant, sensitive to and drawing on the diversity of students.

There is a significant body of research focussing on teacher education, which explores the most effective approaches to teaching and learning (Bahr & Mellor, 2016; Fauth et al., 2019; Goldhaber, 2019; Petty, 2009; Stephenson, 2018), but also how affective variables such as “self” and “identity” influences teaching and learning (Hamachek, 1999; Hargreaves, 1998; Sutton & Wheatley, 2003). Various reports from around the world have highlighted the influence of effective and expert teachers on student learning (Barber & Mourshed, 2007; Hamachek, 1999; Hattie, 2003; H. Slater et al., 2012). This research has informed various teacher standards around the world, which govern various aspects of teaching as a field of study and a career.

At the teacher training level, the standards are governed by the universities and colleges; however, post-graduation teachers are expected to fulfil standards mandate by government bodies, or independent teacher registration organisations. These standards are contextualised to the need of the country or region. However, the underlying philosophical lens across all standards is to ensure that students are taught by qualified and highly trained teachers, who are passionate about education and have the skills to scaffold students in their learning. Furthermore, standards also provide a developmental career roadmap for teachers as they gain experience throughout their career.

Astronomy as a subject encompasses various counter-intuitive concepts. Even though students may have experienced and observed, for example, the passing of the seasons or the phases of the Moon, teaching these concepts to students can be challenging. This is evident in the large body of research on student conceptions in astronomy (e.g.: Bailey et al., 2017; Bektaşlı, 2014; Comins, 2001; Danaia & McKinnon, 2007; Kavanagh et al., 2005; Salimpour, Tytler, et al., 2020; Schneps & Sadler, 1987; E. Slater et al., 2018; T. F. Slater & Gelderman, 2017; Trumper, 2001). Furthermore, teaching concepts in astronomy not only requires deep content knowledge, but also an understanding of how students are able reason and learn. This latter aspect has implications for the manifestation and persistence of alternative conceptions (e.g.: diSessa, 2004; Driver & Easley, 1978; Salimpour, Tytler, et al., 2020; Salimpour, 2021; R. T. White & Gunstone, 1989). Therefore, it is vital to ensure that teachers teaching astronomy topics, are well supported with quality resources, a range of pedagogical strategies, and an understanding of the concepts, to be able to support students in their learning.

There are a range of astronomy teacher training programs around the world that have over the years accumulated vital experience with regards to teacher training in astronomy. Some notable examples include Network for Astronomy School Education (NASE) (Deustua et al., 2014; NASE, 2021), Galileo Teacher Training Program (GTTP) (Doran, 2010; GTTP, 2021), Astronomy from the Ground Up! (CSIRO, 2019), NASA/IPAC Teacher Archive Research Program (NITARP)(Rebull et al., 2018), and Our Solar Siblings (Fitzgerald et al., 2021). In addition to these, there are various regional teacher training programs (e.g.: IAU100, 2019). The key here to take the lessons learned from all these programs, together with educational research and determine if there is some commonality that can extracted with regards to the vital characteristics of teacher training programs in astronomy education

Aim of the study

This study aims to explore the landscape of teacher training by soliciting insights from within the IAU and its extended organisational network. In doing so, this study aims to answer the below research questions:

- What is the current landscape of teacher training workshops within, and related to, the IAU?
- To what extent can overarching themes be identified to inform the development of teacher training standards?
- What are the concerns and challenges with regards to developing and implementing teacher training standards in astronomy education?

Methodology

This exploratory study used an online questionnaire comprising of multiple-choice and open-ended questions. The survey sampling involved members of the International Astronomical Union, and adherences to the IAU offices family (OAO, OAD, OAE). In total, 56 respondents, from 34 countries completed the survey (Fig. 1). Although the number of respondents was low compared to the number of members in the IAU network, this is not an issue given the exploratory nature of the study.

The analysis involved a mixed-methods approach, where the multiple-choice responses provided quantitative information about distributions, whereas the open-ended responses provided both qualitative and quantitative information. The open-ended responses were iteratively coded to identify over-arching themes, and the underlying distributions within those themes were explored.

Figure 1: Global distribution of respondents who took the survey.

Results

Some of the key results from this study are summarised in the following sections. The results provide an exploratory snapshot of the current state of teacher training workshops in astronomy education in the context of the IAU and its extended organisational network. The results are grouped into overall categories based on the questions in the survey.

Demographics

Survey Respondents

The respondents covered a range of backgrounds from those involved in teacher training, astronomers, university and research institution staff, volunteers and amateur societies. Given the nature of astronomy as field that has both strong professional and amateur communities, it is not surprising to see this diversity in respondents. More importantly, the survey was aimed at members of the IAU community and as such was limited to those involved either with the IAU or its offices and network (Fig.2). That said, the IAU offices cover a diversity of individuals all of whom are active in the field of astronomy outreach and education.

Figure 2: Respondent distribution for the survey. NAEC (National Astronomy Education Coordinator); NOC (National Outreach Coordinator); OAD (Office of Astronomy for Development); ROAD (Regional Office of Astronomy for Development). The grouping of respondent roles within the IAU network is because respondents could select multiple roles.

Teacher Training Instructors

The teacher training instructors who run workshops in astronomy education were diverse in their background; however, given the sampling the majority were either professional astronomers who are active in outreach and/or certified teachers (Fig. 3). The Other category included: science communicators, informal educators, inactive professional astronomers, interested college faculty, and career change astronomers.

Figure 3: Distribution of the background of Teacher Training Instructors using individual options in isolation. The percentages can add to more the 100%, and that is due to the fact that respondents could select multiple options.

Teachers attending training

The teachers who participated in the teacher training workshops cover a diverse range with the majority being Primary and/or Secondary teachers (Fig. 4). There seems to be interest among amateur astronomers and undergraduate faculty (Fig. 5).

Figure 4: Distribution of teachers attending training categorised into Primary, Secondary, those that are Primary & Secondary trained, and Other. The percentages can add to more the 100%, and that is due to the fact that respondents could select multiple options.

Figure 5: The diverse range of individuals that attend teacher training workshops who selected Other.

Although some workshops are attended by Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) teachers, majority of training workshops have a diverse range of teachers that includes both STEM and non-STEM teachers (Fig. 6) This latter aspect is interesting because teachers attending may not necessarily have a good grasp of the astronomy content. The reason for this is that teachers teaching astronomy, especially in lower year levels, may not have any training in science. Therefore, teacher training workshops must aim to find ways in creating a balance between teaching the teachers the astronomical content and how to best enable them to teach the astronomical concepts. Being proficient in the content does not necessarily make the teacher efficient at teaching the concepts, thus teacher training workshops need to make use of the in-class teaching experience of the teachers.

The prominence of Physics (~43%) teachers is an important point, this is because Physics teachers are often the most interested in astronomy, and astronomy often appears in Physics curricula (Salimpour, Bartlett, et al., 2020). One factor that may contribute to this number is perhaps due to the out-of-field scenario that exists in many countries (e.g.: Hobbs & Porsch, 2021; Hobbs & Törner, 2019). One possible hypothesis is that the Physics teachers attending these workshops are perhaps not trained in Physics or even science, but they have to teach science at lower grades. When looking at curricula around the world, most of the astronomy topics are present in primary to middle school (Salimpour, Bartlett, et al., 2020). There is evidence from research that number of out-of-field teachers in Physics has increased (Claes & Pedersen, 2018; Shah et al., 2019; White & Tyler, 2013), the impact this has on the numbers in this survey requires a deeper analysis.

Figure 6: Distribution in the subject speciality of teachers. The results reveal that the majority of teachers are STEM trained, with a clear prominence of Physics teachers.

Training Workshops

Instruction methods in Teacher Training

Given that the teachers attending often have experience of their own classroom environment, it is important to understand what sort of pedagogies are most suited to the teachers. Furthermore, one aspect of teaching training workshops is to also model some of the pedagogies that are more conducive to teaching the complex spatial and temporal relations unique to astronomy. The survey results show that there is a strong focus on Lectures (~75%) and Hands-on (~66%) approaches when teaching the teachers (Fig.7), with some focus on Discussions (~38%).

Figure 7: Distribution in the instructional methods used by the teacher trainers, with the majority using both Lectures and Hands-on approaches.

Resources used in Teacher Training

Alongside pedagogy, teaching resources are perhaps one of the most important components in a teacher’s toolkit. There exists a vast range of resources for teaching astronomy, and organisations such as NASA, ESA, and ESO, have over many years provided a vast array of resources. The challenge for a teacher who is a novice in teaching astronomy is selecting the most effective resource. This has prompted the efforts to bring peer-reviewed astronomy activities to teachers via the astroEDU project (astroEDU, 2021).

The results show that when it comes to IAU resources nearly 95% of the respondents use IAU resources (Fig.8), with top four IAU resources used being astroEDU (~22%), NASE (~20%), UNAW (Universe Awareness) (~17%), and GTTP (~15%). This is not surprising given the target group being surveyed and the fact that these programs have a longstanding history in the astronomy education community.

When it comes to non-IAU resources the results reveal that ~40% of the respondents are using resources by NASA, ~25% using resources from ESA, and ~20% using resources by ESO.

Overall, it can be seen that the majority of respondents are aware of and using a range of astronomy education resources. The next step is providing some framework that allows educators especially the novices to be able to navigate this rich landscape of ever-growing astronomy education resources.

Figure 8: Distribution of IAU resources using in teacher training workshops.

Figure 9: Distribution of the varying types of IAU resources used.

Figure 10: Distribution of Non-IAU resources used in teacher training workshops.

Observational Activities in Teacher Training

Perhaps one of the defining characteristics of astronomy or rather the perception that the public has of astronomy is looking through telescopes. Looking through telescopes is perhaps the highlight of outreach events across the world. However, observational activities in astronomy are not limited to telescopes, rather they are situated on a spectrum that stretches from low-tech to high-tech (Fig. 11). Low-tech observational activities can include unaided-eye observations, making measurements using simple devices, while the high-tech activities extend to not only telescopic observations rather robotic and remote telescopes. Low-tech observational activities are in general more accessible especially in rural and remote regions. However, there has been a global effort to get telescopes to more learners around the world (IAU, 2021). This will in the long run perhaps put telescopes in the realm of “low-tech” astronomy when considering the accessibility aspect.

Figure 11: The spectrum of observational activities.

This survey explored the various ways that teacher training workshops incorporate observational activities into their program. The results show that (~70%) of the workshop include observational activities as part of the training workshop (Fig. 12). When looking at the types of observational activities it can be clearly seen that telescopic observations are the most prevalent (~50%) (Fig. 13). Furthermore, it is also evident that observational activities are not limited to the night, with nearly 35% of them having both daytime and night-time components.

Figure 12: Distribution of respondents who incorporate observational activities in their teacher training workshops.

Figure 13: Distribution of the types of observational activities used in teacher training workshops.

Post Workshops

Education is as much about the “in-training” as it is about the “post-training”, in essence, every teacher would like to know what the students got from the lesson, what was their take on the teaching and their learning? In the broadest sense, this is about evaluation in all its varying forms.

Evaluation is innately connected with feedback and as such provides a means to reflect on what were the conditions that best engaged students as learners. In the context of teacher training, evaluation takes various forms. The most basic is soliciting feedback from the teachers who attended; the next form is assessing the impact of workshop on the teacher’s Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK) (Shulman, 1986); and the final layer is teachers implementing the activities in their own classroom and assessing the impact on their student’s learning.

The results show that all the respondents follow up with teachers post workshop, whether it is regularly or sometimes (Fig. 14). The types of follow-up methods are diverse; however, the majority seem to have some form of further interactions (Fig. 15).

Follow-up methods have with them a socio-cultural dimension, and as such a follow-up method in once context may not strictly apply to another context.

Figure 11: Distribution of respondents who follow-up with teachers post workshop.

Figure 12: Distribution of follow-up methods used by the teacher trainers. There is a strong focus on Social Media, Surveys, and Reflections by attending teachers.

Discussion

Using exploratory data results from this study some over-arching themes could be extracted that perhaps offer points of consideration when developing teacher training standards specific to astronomy education. These themes could apply more broadly to any other discipline if the aim was to develop standards at a global level. The over-arching themes are discussed below with implications for their development. It should be emphasised that whatever shape teaching training standards take, they need to consider notions of equity, diversity, and inclusion as fundamental to their development, and inform all the standards.

The broad nature of these themes is owing to the medium-grain analysis employed in this survey. The aim is in the first instance to provide a relatively “zoomed-out” view of what shape the standards could take. With each iteration and implementation of a refined survey and focussed interviews we can then “zoom-in” towards a finer-grained analysis. The fine-grained analysis will allow specific statements to be developed that help better contextualise each of the over-arching standards.

Taken together the five over-arching themes (standards) that can provide a preliminary framework for developing standards for teacher training in astronomy education are shown in Figure 16.

Figure 13: A preliminary framework for developing Astronomy Education Teacher Training Standards.

Content Standards

Given that the standards are aimed at school level (ages ~5 – 18; grades pre-primary to high school), the Content Standards will need to be guided by the topics that are addressed in curricula around the world (Salimpour, Bartlett, et al., 2020), and also by education research informing the appropriateness of certain topics at various levels. Initial results from curriculum surveys show that while some countries do not have astronomy as a standalone subject, concepts in astronomy are distributed throughout the curriculum in various contexts (Salimpour, Bartlett, et al., 2020). In addition, there is a certain level of homogeneity in curricula with regards to at what levels various topics appear. Therefore, developing content standards would be informed by curricula, and care must be taken to consider that curricula change over time.

Perhaps a deeper consideration would be to take into account the developmental progression of concepts and what a “typical” astronomy curriculum should resemble. Questions need to be asked about the appropriateness of certain topics, not only from the developmental aspect but also from a socio-cultural lens taking into consideration notions of equity, diversity and inclusion. Seasons in every country do not manifest in the same way, and some conceptual aspects of seasons are not “lived experience” for students. Therefore, the Content Standards need to be flexible and consider the various “global” and “local” aspects of astronomy.

The content standards also need to be informed by accurate scientific consensus ideas, and this is where the Big Ideas in Astronomy (Retrê et al., 2019), provides a framework to guide the content standards.

Therefore, developing Content Standards require a three-pronged approach where the foundations are informed by the above three (Fig. 17)

Figure 14: The Content Standards would need to be based on three vital foundations: Curriculum, Education Research, and the Big Ideas in Astronomy.

Teaching Method Standards

Teaching methods are supported by an ever-growing and vast body of research. The efficacy of particular teaching methods will always be the topic of research and debate (e.g.: Anderson, 2002; Clark et al., 2012; Dean Jr. & Kuhn, 2007; Flick, 1995; Furtak et al., 2012; Kirschner et al., 2006; Klahr & Nigam, 2004). This is simply because every classroom context is different, and furthermore, cultural perceptions of teaching and learning vary across the world and various regions. In the context of Science Education, there is a trend towards inquiry and active learning to help foster the epistemic practices of science (Abd-El-Khalick et al., 2004; Barrow, 2006; Cairns & Areepattamannil, 2019; Fitzgerald, 2015), this is also echoed in international policy reports (OECD, 2016). Despite this, there is always a place for the diverse range of teaching methods, and it is at the discretion of the teacher and their skill to choose the ones most appropriate to the students in their class and the aim of their lesson. This is a view that is coherent among practising teachers, who through many years of experience and daily interactions with students, appreciate the complex process of teaching and learning.

This study showed that the lectures and hands-on approaches were the two most prevalent teaching methods employed in teacher training workshops in astronomy education (Fig.7). This is owing to the fact that teachers attending training workshops may not understand the content. Therefore, the approach is to familiarise them with the content, before delving into more hands-on approaches to how they could teach a topic. In addition, it could be argued that in certain countries teachers themselves may be more comfortable with direct instruction and as such that provides a more familiar approach. This is important because teaching has a strong cultural dimension, and it is vital to consider this when developing standards.

Resource Standards

Resources are one of the key aspects of the teaching and learning process and are vital especially for teachers who are new to a topic, subject, or perhaps early-career teachers. In astronomy education, there is a vast number of resources ranging from those produced by organisation like NASA, ESA, ESO all the way to those produced by astronomy teachers. However the quality of resources varies while some are very contextual and may not work in all countries/regions. The astroEDU project which was launched in 2013 is a repository of peer-reviewed astronomy (and space-related) education activities (astroEDU, 2021). astroEDU provides educators access to a diverse range of astronomy education activities that are peer-reviewed by professionals in education and science.

Considering the survey results it is perhaps important for teacher training standards to incorporate what would be considered high-quality resources and ensuring that they are accessible to teachers. One concern is that ensuring the resources are available in a range of languages, which itself could be a barrier in teachers using a particular resource. One way to tackle the language barrier has been implemented by astroEDU, whereby organisations can create an astroEDU platform in their own language, following the framework set out by astroEDU. Currently, astroEDU is available in English, Italian and Korean. Although, there is no doubt high-quality resources are already available in various other languages.

Accreditation Standards

This is a complex standard. Firstly, training programs in some countries and regions need to be accredited by the relevant government body (for example, Ministry of Education). This aspect has been highlighted by respondents to the survey. Secondly, teachers in some countries need to show some form accreditation following their attendance at training workshop, and so they are more likely to attend training workshops that are accredited and provide accreditation (Fig. 18).

Another aspect that was identified through the responses in the survey, was that training workshops that are supported by the IAU OAE would be more likely to gain accreditation in the relevant countries and/or regions (Fig. 19)

Figure 15: Distribution of respondents based on whether programs require accreditation

Figure 16: Results from the question asking respondents whether support from the OAE would make it easier for their training workshop to gain accreditation. It can be seen the majority would welcome OAE support.

Based on the survey results there are two aspects to accreditation. Firstly, accreditation given from workshops to the attendees that they have participated in a workshop that aligns with the relevant educational framework of that country, this is usually in the form of a certificate. This first aspect of accreditation is perhaps “simpler” in the sense that if an astronomy teacher training workshop is endorsed by, for example, the IAU, then the workshop can issue attendees certificates of attendance. This provides the teachers with some tangible certification for their teaching portfolio, which they can present to their school leadership.

The second aspect of accreditation is the one that is slightly more complex and is determined by the relevant Ministry of Education. In this case, the workshop the teacher is attending is certified by the Ministry or other relevant organisation. An example of this second aspect can be seen in Australia where the New South Wales Department of Education lists all the courses that certified by the department, and count towards the hours required for teacher professional development (New South Wales Department of Education, 2022).

Owing to the above aspects, accreditation standards can be achieved to a certain extent, and it involves engaging with the relevant educational authorities (or indirectly via the OAE NAECs) in various countries to get an idea about what could be feasible.

Educator Standards

The effectiveness of an instructor to help students through the learning journey is dependent on various internal and external factors, one of which is the skill and pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) (Shulman, 1986) of the teacher. In considering these internal and external factors, various countries have developed Teacher Professional Standards that provide teachers with a scaffolding for development in teaching practice. For example, in Australia, the Australian Institute for Teaching and School Leadership (AITSL) through iterative cycles and informed by education research has developed standards for Teachers and Principals (AITSL, 2018). The teacher standards comprise of seven overarching standards that have four levels of proficiency (Graduate, Proficient, High Accomplished, and Lead). Similarly in the United Kingdom there is the Teacher Standards (Department

for Education, 2016, 2021), and in Germany there is the Standards für die Lehrerbildung: Bildungswissenschaften (Standards for teacher training: Educational sciences (KMK, 2014).

Furthermore, universities and colleges that provide teacher training, also have a set of standards that graduates must meet to qualify as teachers. In various countries obtaining a registration to teach, requires teachers to demonstrate certain requirements and there is a yearly re-registration process.

Taking the above into consideration and looking at the background of teacher trainers (Fig.3), it is important to consider what types of Educator Standards could be considered and viable when developing the Astronomy Education Teacher Training Standards that have the potential to be used globally. A few respondents highlighted that the educator needs to have the appropriate content knowledge and this, when contextualised in teaching, requires the educator have the appropriate PCK. This means that knowing the content as astronomers do is perhaps not enough to be able to teach teachers how to teach the content. Having astronomers working in tandem with an educator allows for a powerful approach to teacher training workshops. Furthermore, PCK also considers the contextualisation aspect, where it is important to “know the learners”.

Concerns and Challenges

The word “standards” can be perceived as a burden, and as such there is often a heated debate when new standards are introduced, whether it is in the context of curriculum (e.g.: Moore et al., 2003) or other aspects of education (e.g.: Tuinamuana, 2011). This is because although standards are intended to guide and support, they often evolve into extra work for teachers, and become restrictive (Moore et al., 2003).

It is therefore not surprising, that developing standards, which can be applied globally will no doubt present challenges. This is perhaps equal in the same respect to defining the qualities of what it means to be “a good teacher” (Korthagen, 2004). Although, from a policy perspective national teacher standards may have provided a guiding framework, and research has provided some insights, the art of being a “good” teacher is complex. However, it could be argued that one characteristic is the ability to maintain a plurality of approaches in teaching and learning.

Although, the themes identified in the report can be seen in the responses, there were some concerns raised as to the efficacy and viability of having AETTS in the strict sense of “standards”. The key concern was related to the notion of diversity in its broadest sense. Given that education systems and teaching methods are so varied across the world, owing to cultural diversity, would imposing standards be contradictory to notions of equity, diversity, and inclusion? For example, although inquiry-based learning may be prominent in some education systems, it may not be appropriate in other education systems. In essence, having standards that are too restrictive may be challenging to implement globally, and would dissuade teacher trainers and teachers from adhering to those standards. This lack of diversity was also described with regards to training workshops not having control over what and how they conduct their workshops. This perhaps raises concerns with regards to the notion of “decolonisation” (Battiste, 2019; Smith, 2021) , which one dimension of ensuring education is equitable, diverse, and inclusive.

Therefore, it is vital that the “standards” presented here encapsulated by the five overarching themes, and the final form be considered from the perspective of recommendations, and support rather than mandated rules. They provide a framework to inform

effective and appropriate teacher training, rather than standards in the strictest sense, that are mandated. More importantly, one of the key foundations vital to the process of developing standards and the standards themselves is the notion of transparency. This ensures that the challenges that arise due to diversity can be made explicit in a way that maintains the richness of diversity.

Transparency can manifest in different ways, and there are various ways it can be addressed. This could be as simple as keeping robust records. In the context of a teacher training workshop, this could be in the form of publishing the results from an evaluation. One thing that as a community we need to be aware of is transparency morphing into “unintentional control”, which echoes responses that highlighted their concern with regards to standards becoming a form of control. This latter aspect needs to be discussed more broadly within the community to ensure the level of “standardisation” with which the community is comfortable.

Conclusion

This exploratory study aimed to identify the current landscape of teacher training within the IAU and its extended organisational network which includes the OAO, OAD and OAE.

The analysis of responses from an online survey identified five overarching themes that can be used to inform the development of teaching training standards for astronomy education: Content Standards, Teaching Method Standards, Resource Standards, Accreditation Standards, and Educator Standards. Although, these standards were recommended, there were also concerns raised about imposing standards that may not be appropriate given the rich diversity across the world. We are not dealing with robots, but autonomous human beings and in the context of teaching and learning, it is imperative to consider this rich, dynamic context, by ensuring that the standards are flexible enough to make allowance for this dynamism.

The next stage will involve using the insights from this survey to develop preliminary finer-grained statements for each of the standards and to iteratively refine the standards using a Delphi Study approach. This involves focussed interviews and surveys that allows input from the broader astronomy, astronomy education and education communities.

References

- Abd-El-Khalick, F., BouJaoude, S., Duschl, R., Lederman, N. G., Mamlok-Naaman, R., Hofstein, A., Niaz, M., Treagust, D., & Tuan, H. (2004). Inquiry in science education: International perspectives. *Science Education*, 88(3), 397–419. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sce.10118>
- AITSL. (2018). *Australian Professional Standards for Teachers*. Australian Institute for Teaching and School Leadership. https://www.aitsl.edu.au/docs/default-source/national-policy-framework/australian-professional-standards-for-teachers.pdf?sfvrsn=580of33c_80
- Anderson, R. D. (2002). Reforming Science Teaching: What Research says about Inquiry. *Journal of Science Teacher Education*, 13(1), 1–12.
- astroEDU. (2021). *What is astroEDU? | astroEDU*. <https://astroedu.iau.org/en/about/>
- Bahr, N., & Mellor, S. (2016). *Building quality in teaching and teacher education (Australian Council for Educational Research)*.
- Bailey, J. M., Lombardi, D., Cordova, J. R., & Sinatra, G. M. (2017). Meeting students halfway: Increasing self-efficacy and promoting knowledge change in astronomy. *Physical Review Physics Education Research*, 13(2), 020140. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevPhysEducRes.13.020140>
- Barber, M., & Mourshed, M. (2007). *How the world's best-performing school systems come out on top*.
- Barrow, L. H. (2006). A Brief History of Inquiry: From Dewey to Standards. *Journal of Science Teacher Education*, 17(3), 265–278. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10972-006-9008-5>
- Bektaşlı, B. (2014). In-Service Science Teachers' Astronomy Misconceptions. *Akdeniz Eğitim Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 8(15), 1–10.
- Cairns, D., & Aarepattamannil, S. (2019). Exploring the Relations of Inquiry-Based Teaching to Science Achievement and Dispositions in 54 Countries. *Research in Science Education*, 49(1), 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11165-017-9639-x>
- Claes, D. R., & Pedersen, J. E. (2018). Physics Teachers as Physics Experts: Research Participation as Professional Development. *Science Educator*, 26(2), 12.
- Clark, R. E., Kirschner, P. A., & Sweller, J. (2012). Putting Students on the Path to Learning: The Case for Fully Guided Instruction. *American Educator*, 36(1), 6–11.
- Comins, N. F. (2001). *Sources of Misconceptions in Astronomy*. 38.
- CSIRO. (2019). *Astronomy from the Ground Up! 2019 Teacher Workshop*. https://www.atnf.csiro.au/news/news.php?action=show_item&item_id=1707
- Danaia, L., & McKinnon, D. H. (2007). Common Alternative Astronomical Conceptions Encountered in Junior Secondary Science Classes: Why Is This So? *Astronomy Education Review*, 6(2), 32–53. <https://doi.org/10.3847/AER2007017>
- Dean Jr., D., & Kuhn, D. (2007). Direct instruction vs. discovery: The long view. *Science Education*, 91(3), 384–397. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sce.20194>
- Department for Education. (2016). *Standard for teachers' professional development*. London: United Kingdom
- Department for Education. (2021). *Teachers' Standards*. London: United Kingdom
- Deustua, S. E., Ros, R. M., & Garcia, B. (2014). *Network for Astronomy School Education*. American Astronomical Meeting Abstracts 223, 449.03.
- diSessa, A. A. (2004). Metarepresentation: Native Competence and Targets for Instruction. *Cognition and Instruction*, 22(3), 293–331. https://doi.org/10.1207/s1532690xci2203_2
- Doran, R. (2010). *The Galileo Teacher Training Programme*. 38, 2.
- Driver, R., & Easley, J. (1978). Pupils and Paradigms: A Review of Literature Related to Concept Development in Adolescent Science Students. *Studies in Science Education*, 5(1), 61–84. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03057267808559857>

- Fauth, B., Decristan, J., Decker, A.-T., Büttner, G., Hardy, I., Klieme, E., & Kunter, M. (2019). The effects of teacher competence on student outcomes in elementary science education: The mediating role of teaching quality. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 86, 102882. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2019.102882>
- Fitzgerald, M. T. (2015). *Design Principles, Implementation And Evaluation For Inquiry-Based Astronomy*. Ph.D. Thesis. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.32534>
- Fitzgerald, M. T., McKinnon, D., Danaia, L., Salimpour, S., & Cutts, K. R. (2021). *Online Courses for Teachers, Students and the Public – Our Solar Siblings*. <https://www.oursolarsiblings.com/online-courses/>
- Flick, L. B. (1995). *Complex Instruction in Complex Classrooms: A Synthesis of Research on Inquiry Teaching Methods and Explicit Teaching Strategies*. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED383563>
- Furtak, E. M., Seidel, T., Iverson, H., & Briggs, D. C. (2012). Experimental and Quasi-Experimental Studies of Inquiry-Based Science Teaching: A Meta-Analysis. *Review of Educational Research*, 82(3), 300–329. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654312457206>
- Goldhaber, D. (2019). Evidence-Based Teacher Preparation: Policy Context and What We Know. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 70(2), 90–101. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022487118800712>
- GTPP. (2021). Galileo Teacher Training Program | A legacy of the International Year of Astronomy 2009. <http://galileoteachers.org/>
- Hamachek, D. (1999). *Effective teachers: What they do, how they do it, and the importance of self-knowledge*. In R. P. Lipka & T. M. Brinthaupt (Eds.), *The role of self in teacher development* (pp. 189–224).
- Hargreaves, A. (1998). The emotional practice of teaching. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 14(8), 835–854. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0742-051X\(98\)00025-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0742-051X(98)00025-0)
- Hattie, J. (2003). Teachers Make a Difference, What is the research evidence? *ACER Conference Series*, 18.
- Hobbs, L., & Porsch, R. (2021). Teaching out-of-field: Challenges for teacher education. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 44(5), 601–610. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02619768.2021.1985280>
- Hobbs, L., & Törner, G. (2019). *Examining the phenomenon of “teaching out-of-field”: International perspectives on teaching as a non-specialist*. Springer.
- IAU. (2021). *Telescopes for All An IAU Global Outreach Project*. <https://www.iau.org/public/telescopecollaboration/>
- IAU100. (2019). *ArAS Astronomy Teacher Training | IAU100: Under One Sky*. <https://www.iau-100.org/aras-teacher-training>
- Kavanagh, C., Agan, L., & Sneider, C. (2005). Learning about Phases of the Moon and Eclipses: A Guide for Teachers and Curriculum Developers. *Astronomy Education Review*, 4(1), 19–52. <https://doi.org/10.3847/AER2005002>
- Kirschner, P. A., Sweller, J., & Clark, R. E. (2006). Why minimal guidance during instruction does not work: An analysis of the failure of constructivist, discovery, problem-based, experiential, and inquiry-based teaching. *Educational Psychologist*, 41(2), 75–86.
- Klahr, D., & Nigam, M. (2004). The Equivalence of Learning Paths in Early Science Instruction: Effects of Direct Instruction and Discovery Learning. *Psychological Science*, 15(10), 661–667. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0956-7976.2004.00737.x>
- KMK. (2014). *Standards for teacher training: Educational sciences*.
- Korthagen, F. A. J. (2004). In search of the essence of a good teacher: Towards a more holistic approach in teacher education. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 20(1), 77–97. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2003.10.002>
- Moore, R., Jensen, M., & Hatch, J. (2003). The Problems with State Educational Standards. *Science Education Review*, 2(3). <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1058495>
- NASE. (2021). NASE: Network for Astronomy School Education. <http://sac.csic.es/astrosecundaria/en/Presentacion.php>
- New South Wales Department of Education. (2022). *Professional Learning for schools*. NSW Department of Education. <https://education.nsw.gov.au/teaching-and-learning/professional-learning.html>

- OECD. (2016). *PISA 2015 Results (Volume II): Policies and Practices for Successful Schools*. <https://www.oecd.org/education/pisa-2015-results-volume-ii-9789264267510-en.htm>
- Petty. (2009). *Evidence-Based Teaching: A Practical Approach* (2nd Revised edition). Oxford University Press UK.
- Rebull, L., French, D., Laurence, W., Roberts, T., Fitzgerald, M., Gorjian, V., & Squires, G. (2018). Major outcomes of an authentic astronomy research experience professional development program: An analysis of 8 years of data from a teacher research program. *Physical Review Physics Education Research*, 14(2), 020102.
- Retrê, J., Russo, P., Lee, H., Penteadó, E., Salimpour, S., Fitzgerald, M., Ramchandani, J., Pössel, M., Scorza, C., Christensen, L., Arends, E., Pompea, S., & Schrier, W. (2019). *Big Ideas in Astronomy: A Proposed Definition of Astronomy Literacy*.
- Salimpour, S. (2021). *Visualising the Cosmos: Teaching cosmology in high school in the era of big data* [Doctoral Thesis]. Deakin University.
- Salimpour, S., Bartlett, S., Fitzgerald, M. T., McKinnon, D. H., Cutts, K. R., James, C. R., Miller, S., Danaia, L., Hollow, R. P., Cabezon, S., Faye, M., Tomita, A., Max, C., de Korte, M., Baudouin, C., Birkenbauma, D., Kallery, M., Anjos, S., Wu, Q., ... Ortiz-Gil, A. (2020). The gateway science: A review of astronomy in the OECD school curricula, including China and South Africa. *Research in Science Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11165-020-09922-0>
- Salimpour, S., Tytler, R., & Fitzgerald, M. T. (2020). Exploring the Cosmos: The Challenge of Identifying Patterns and Conceptual Progressions from Student Survey Responses in Cosmology. In R. Tytler, P. White, J. Ferguson, & J. C. Clark (Eds.), *Methodological Approaches to STEM Education Research (Vol. 1)*. Cambridge University Press.
- Schneps, M., & Sadler, P. M. (1987). *A Private Universe*. <https://www.learner.org/resources/series28.html#>
- Shah, L., Jannuzzo, C., Hassan, T., Gadidov, B., Ray, H. E., & Rushton, G. T. (2019). Diagnosing the current state of out-of-field teaching in high school science and mathematics. *PLOS ONE*, 14(9), e0223186. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0223186>
- Shuell, T. J. (2001). Teaching and Learning in the Classroom. In N. J. Smelser & P. B. Baltes (Eds.), *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences* (pp. 15468–15472). Pergamon. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B0-08-043076-7/02449-9>
- Shulman, L. S. (1986). Those Who Understand: Knowledge Growth in Teaching. *Educational Researcher*, 15(2), 4–14. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X015002004>
- Slater, E., Morris, J., & McKinnon, D. H. (2018). Astronomy alternative conceptions in pre-adolescent students in Western Australia. *International Journal of Science Education*, 0(0), 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500693.2018.1522014>
- Slater, H., Davies, N. M., & Burgess, S. (2012). Do Teachers Matter? Measuring the Variation in Teacher Effectiveness in England*. *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics*, 74(5), 629–645. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-0084.2011.00666.x>
- Slater, T. F., & Gelderman, R. (2017). Addressing Students' Misconceptions about Eclipses. *Physics Teacher*, 55(5), 314–315. <https://doi.org/10.1119/1.4981046>
- Stephenson, J. (2018). A Systematic Review of the Research on the Knowledge and Skills of Australian Preservice Teachers. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 43(4), 121–137. <https://doi.org/10.14221/ajte.2018v43n4.7>
- Sutton, R. E., & Wheatley, K. F. (2003). Teachers' Emotions and Teaching: A Review of the Literature and Directions for Future Research. *Educational Psychology Review*, 15(4), 327–358. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1026131715856>
- Trumper, R. (2001). A cross-age study of junior high school students' conceptions of basic astronomy concepts. *International Journal of Science Education*, 23(11), 1111–1123. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500690010025085>
- Tuinamuana, K. (2011). Teacher Professional Standards, Accountability, and Ideology: Alternative Discourses. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 36(12). <https://doi.org/10.14221/ajte.2011v36n12.8>
- White, R. T., & Gunstone, R. F. (1989). Metalearning and conceptual change. *International Journal of Science Education*, 11(5), 577–586. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0950069890110509>
- White, S., & Tyler, J. (2013). The 2013 Nationwide Survey of High School Physics Teachers. *The Physics Teacher*, 51(1), 52–52. <https://doi.org/10.1119/1.4772042>